

NOTES

High Spin Cobalt(II) Complexes of Substituted 4-Arylazopyrazol-5-ones

H. S. VERMA*, R. C. SAXENA** and K. C. MATHUR**

Department of Chemistry, J. V. College, Baraut-250 611
and

G. S. SHAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

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COMPLEXES of cobalt(II) with 3-methyl-4-(*p*-methyl/*p*-methoxy/*o*-methoxy phenylazo) pyrazol-5-one and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(*o*-carboxyphenylazo) pyrazol-5-one have been prepared and studied through elemental analysis, magnetic measurements and spectral studies. The substituted azopyrazol-5-ones were prepared as in literature¹. Cobalt(II) chloride hexa hydrate used was AnalaR BDH and all the other chemicals were of reagent grade.

The complexes were prepared by the slow addition of aqueous sodium hydroxide (0.1M, 2 ml) to the dioxan-water mixture (100 ml, 3 : 1) containing 3-methyl-4(*p*-methyl/*p*-methoxy/*o*-methoxy phenylazo) pyrazol-5-one or 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4(*o*-carboxyphenylazo) pyrazol-5-one and cobalt(II) chloride hexa hydrate (0.001 mole) at 30° (pH ~ 6.0). The contents were refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr. The thick coloured precipitate obtained on cooling was filtered, washed with cold alcohol and finally with ether. The chelates were crystallised from DMF-methanol mixture and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The elemental analysis and physical measurements viz., magnetic moment, conductance, infrared and absorption spectra etc. were recorded as described earlier².

Results and Discussion

Analytical results show 1 : 2 metal to ligand stoichiometry. All the complexes are insoluble in water but soluble in DMF. All the coloured complexes are fairly stable. The purity of these complexes was checked by tlc. The analytical and electronic spectral data do not show the presence of any Co(III) admixed with Co(II). The complexes (a), (b) and (c) show their magnetic moment values in the range (4.1-4.8 B.M.) expected for tetrahedral geometry. These values are higher than the spin only value (3.89 B.M.) due to high orbital contribution and is attributed to the three fold orbital degeneracy of the ⁴T_{1g} ground state. But the complex (d) has a magnetic moment value (5.00 B.M.) which corresponds to octahedral geometry (Table 1). The molar conductance values in DMF at 10⁻³M show that the complexes (a), (b) and (c) are non-electrolytes but the complex (d) is bi-univalent in nature. The acidic nature of the complex (d) was also noticed as it gave effervescence with sodium bicarbonate. The presence of two hydrogen ions was estimated pH-metrically by titrating the complex solution with potassium hydroxide. The complex exhibited sharp inflection at m=2 (where m is the mole of base added per mole of the complex).

In the electronic spectra of the complexes (a), (b) and (c) three principal bands are observed in the region 5320-7200 cm⁻¹ (ν₁), 9790-10380 cm⁻¹ (ν₂) and 16490-26000 cm⁻¹ (ν₃) which could be assigned to ⁴A_{2g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F); ⁴A_{2g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(F) and ⁴A_{2g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(P) respectively in a tetrahedral geometry³. The values of 10 Dq, Racah's parameter (B) and nephelauxetic effect (β) have been evaluated. The value of B for all these complexes is less than the free ion value (971 cm⁻¹) and the value of β is between 0.5-1.0 indicating the partial

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, FORMULAE AND OTHER PROPERTIES OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Analysis*				m.p.	μ _{eff}
		%M	%O	%H	%N		
(a) [Co(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ O) ₂]	dark brown	12.14 (12.06)	26.78 (26.99)	2.20 (2.24)	11.64 (11.45)	285	4.20
(b) [Co(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂) ₂]	violet	11.58 (11.67)	26.26 (26.14)	2.14 (2.17)	10.98 (11.05)	290	4.73
(c) [Co(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂) ₂]	purple	11.74 (11.67)	26.30 (26.14)	2.12 (2.17)	11.16 (11.05)	300	4.63
(d) [Co(C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂) ₂]H ₂	brown	8.26 (8.38)	28.82 (29.02)	1.86 (1.99)	7.84 (7.96)	300	5.00

* Theoretical values are in parenthesis.

* For correspondence.

** Present Address : Department of Chemistry, M. M. College, Modinagar-201 204.

covalent character of the bond concerned. In the electronic spectrum of the complex (d) also, three bands are observed in the region 7000 cm^{-1} (ν_1), 18600 cm^{-1} (ν_2) and 21000 cm^{-1} (ν_3) attributed to the assignments ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$; ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively showing octahedral symmetry. The ligand field parameters $10 Dq$ and B have been calculated with the help of the expressions available in literature⁴.

On examination of the ir spectra of the ligands and their corresponding complexes with cobalt(II) it has been found that most of the frequencies are perturbed on complexation. The lowering of the frequencies in the order of 50 cm^{-1} for $>C=O$ and $20\text{-}25\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $-N=N-$ respectively during chelation indicates that these two groups are participating in the reaction. The antisymmetric carbonyl stretch of the $-COOH$ at 1680 cm^{-1} is replaced by a very strong band at 1580 cm^{-1} in the complex (d). This is due to the antisymmetric stretch of the coordinated carboxylate ion. The coordination through oxygen atom of carboxyl group is further supported by the disappearance of $-OH$ deformation vibrations^{5,6}. Several new bands at $480\text{-}510\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $450\text{-}475\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to ν_{Co-N} and ν_{Co-O} respectively.

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Spectral, Magnetic and Thermal Studies of Some Transition Metal Ions with N-m-Tolyl-p-Methoxy Benzohydroxamic Acid (TMBHA)

NARAYAN S. BHAVE and R. B. KHARAT

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

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NUMBER of hydroxamic acids have been found in microorganism products¹ of pharmacological and analytical^{2,3} interest. Complex formation studies of hydroxamic acids with several metal ions in solution have been undertaken by various workers⁴⁻⁸. However, not much attention has been paid to the structural studies of solid complexes of hydroxamic acid with transition metal ions. In most of the cases the studies are restricted to colour, solubility and elemental analysis of solid complex formed. In very few cases spectral and magnetic studies have been undertaken for their characterisation⁹⁻¹¹. Recently N-m-tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic acid (TMBHA) has been used in this laboratory^{4,6}

as an analytical reagent. In the present report we describe the chelating ability and tentative geometry of the N-m-tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic acid with some transition metal ions on the basis of elemental, conductance, thermal analysis, magnetic and spectral (electronic, ir, esr) data.

Experimental

Materials and methods: All chemicals were of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. The ligand N-m-tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic acid was prepared by known method^{4,12}.

Preparation of metal chelates: Metal salts of Fe(II), Fe(III) were taken as ferrous ammonium sulphate and ferric nitrate respectively, while the metal salts of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) were used in the form their acetates. Solutions of metal salts were prepared in distilled water and the ligand solution in ethyl alcohol.

Alcoholic solution of ligand and aqueous solution of metal salt were mixed in 2 : 1 (L : M) ratio for Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) chelates and 3 : 1 (L : M) in case of Fe(III) chelate and digested on boiling water bath for about 15 min. The separated complexes were filtered and washed several times with hot water and finally with aqueous ethanol (1 : 1) and dried in desiccator over calcium chloride. The purity of the metal chelates was tested by thin layer chromatography.

Physical measurements: Electronic spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded on Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer in methanol (250-1000 nm). A Carl Zeiss USU-2p spectrophotometer was used for measurement of reflectance spectra (400-1000 nm). IR spectra (nujol mull) were recorded on Specord IR-75 at CIC, Nagpur. Magnetic measurements of all the complexes were made at room temperature and Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes were studied down to liquid nitrogen temperature with Gouy balance at Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay. Diamagnetic constants were calculated by the method given in literature¹³. The esr spectra of the Cu(II) chelates was obtained from the L. I. T., Bombay. Conductance measurements were made using a Toshniwal Conductivity Meter at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with conventional closed type cell. Elemental analysis were performed at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. TG and dta studies were performed as described earlier¹⁴.

Results and Discussion

Analytical results and some physical properties of the complexes are shown in Table I. All the complexes are stable in air and Fe(II), Fe(III) and Cu(II) complexes are soluble in common organic solvents. Complexes of Co(II) and Ni(II) are slightly soluble in chloroform, acetone, DMF and ethanol but soluble in methanol, benzene, nitrobenzene. Molar conductance values in nitrobenzene,